

TrafficIQ: The Traffic Dilemma

Syed Ali Asghar Naqvi (24089431)

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Abstract

Urban traffic congestion is a perennial issue in cities worldwide, causing delays, pollution, stress, and safety risks for road users and pedestrians. This study proposes TrafficIQ's AI-based smart signal system to address these issues. The system predicts future traffic volume and frequency using historical data and dynamically adjusts signal timing to optimize vehicle flow. It also monitors minor accidents and pedestrian traffic to reduce accidents and unnecessary delays. The research involves a comprehensive analysis of current literature, reviewing current traffic management initiatives and infrastructure, policy, and technology uptake gaps. Methodology involves phased rollout, data-driven modeling, and stakeholder coordination to enable realistic integration in city centers. Findings demonstrate that smart signals can greatly impact traffic efficiency, enhance safety for pedestrians, and help move emergency vehicles. Its potential as a sustainable, scalable intelligent solution for urban mobility and smart congestion management is underscored by the findings.

1 Introduction

In an article by INRIX [5], the top 3 cities in terms of traffic congestion were Istanbul, New York and Chicago. Expanding road lanes alone does not solve the underlying problem. There is a need for a permanent, solid solution. That is the goal of our research and the sole problem the company, TrafficIQ is trying to solve.

According to a research conducted by Ankit [3], and his co-authors, while discussing the cause of sudden traffic jams, concluded that chaotic driving but more importantly mismanagement is the leading cause of intense traffic jams in cities and this necessitates improved traffic management strategies. Now cities in countries like India, Pakistan or Bangladesh where the lack of infrastructure enabling better management is worrisome yet understandable. However, it is also a problem for big cities whether they are in Europe or America.

In a discussion by TimeOut [6], it was highlighted that even cities like Berlin, Warsaw and Brussels face traffic congestion and according to the recent numbers London was at the top of the list for being the most congested city in Europe. Population density, limited road capacity and traffic mismanagement when combined play a significant role in this congestion. So regardless of the country or the infrastructure of public transport of the city, traffic congestion is always a problem in most cases.

Hence, the scope of this project undertaken by Traffic IQ is to mitigate the problem of traffic congestion. I shall be determining that by proposing an AI-powered solution which we call as smart signals. The smart signals have the capability of detecting the incoming traffic and predicting the volume and frequency of vehicles based on historical data resulting in an infrastructure where traffic flows freely in addition to that the second cause of traffic congestion is also addressed which is minor accidents which are often caused by pedestrians and such. Therefore, our smart signals not only propose to offer a smooth flow of traffic but a smooth flow of pedestrians as well.

Therefore, to explore more deeply and propose a feasible solution to this problem this paper is divided into 6 parts which are the literature review, the definition of the problem, methodology, technology selection, challenges, implementation plan and finally the conclusion.

2 Literature Review

Review existing literature on AI adoption in business, challenges, and best practices. Discuss relevant case studies or examples. Identify gaps in current knowledge that your project addresses. You should aim for at least 10 academic references to be properly cited in the final paper

In order to introduce a smart system we first need to analyze the infrastructure. Oyewale [1] Found the basis of infrastructure for such smart systems to be integrated into a smart city. The gist of the research was the precipitation of traffic management stakeholders and their acceptance to the adoption of hybrid AI techniques. Through certain surveys and further research it was concluded that perceived ease of use has a positive effect on attitude of use.

This translates to if something is hard to use then people will resist or reject it. In our case, we are adopting a similar approach, preferences for autonomy rejects the idea of resistance. In another study, Nasim [8], explores the need for AI technology to be integrated into the traffic system pointing out the facts that increase in population, globalization and mismanagement leads to traffic congestion which in turn leads to pollution, stress and productivity loss. The author notes that the mere potential of AI to manage traffic without any kind of external forces like human intervention is unexplored although such systems and AI models are being developed. However, the paper draws attention to the challenges faced by AI applications regardless of the promise to alleviate congestion and improve traffic flow.

Moreover, Piotr [11] while studying the problems with implementation of sustainable urban mobility advocated the fact that increase in the number of private cars combined with a developing road network is resulting in an urban sprawl which in turn results in traffic congestion. This is one of the reasons for it. Although done on a national level this study still provides valuable input to the root of the problem of why traffic congestion is such a big issue and what is causing it.

3 Problem Statement

As mentioned previously, traffic jams are increasing in urban areas without any solid solution observed in the distant future. The traffic jam is the root to all kinds of problems from pollution to roadside incidents to a hectic urban environment creating stress and panic.

In addition to that, there are long and useless waiting times for pedestrians which result in jumping of signals and that results in unfortunate mishaps, similarly emergency vehicles have no priority when it comes to the actual management of traffic they rely on the driver in front to make way for them. Hence, these are the main and critical problems when combined form a huge chaos on urban roads and also are the problems the proposed solution will address. This project aims to target a number of gaps and voids in current knowledge as well as target market niches that are not as saturated. As previously implemented, increasing the lanes won't have any effect on the traffic jam. We propose an AI-powered solution so traffic in urban areas can be monitored and can help municipalities to optimize traffic flow.

The core objective of the analysis is to help mitigate or reduce traffic in big cities. The primary cause of traffic jams is traffic overload. Currently aiming to come up with a solution in South-East Asia because of sheer population and extreme traffic jams. Firstly, we are proposing a comprehensive AI-powered solution that merges traffic flow along with pedestrian

crossing and safety focusing on multiple aspects of urban mobility. Secondly, our aim is to explore machine learning techniques to develop a system which is effective, sophisticated and robust hence providing valuable insights into such systems for future works.

4 Methodology

The following section covers the use case scenario, the technology selection and feasibility followed by the implementation plan.

4.1 Use Case Overview

AI can be pivotal in traffic management by providing data driven intelligent solutions. These are the key objectives of the proposed solution

- **Dynamic Traffic Signal Control:** Through real-time traffic flow data, traffic signal timings are adjusted. Signal changes at intersections are optimized to ensure a smooth flow and avoid major traffic jams. This is done by using historical data to predict patterns that may form due to factors such as peak hours.
- **Incident Management:** Roadside incidents often lead to traffic jams due to panic or curiosity from the public, forming bottlenecks. If any roadside incidents or anomalies occur, they are promptly reported to the relevant authorities. Traffic signals are then managed dynamically to ensure that the traffic flow remains unaffected.
- **Traffic Demand Forecasting:** By analyzing historical data, local events, and weather patterns, AI can predict peak traffic periods and generate essential forecasts. This predictive capability is a key objective of the proposed solution.
- **Real-time Traffic Flow Prediction:** Real-time data from traffic sensors, cameras, and GPS devices is analyzed to provide insights for route planning. This enables drivers to choose optimal routes, thereby reducing congestion and travel time. It also helps private car owners avoid high-traffic areas in advance.

4.2 Technology Selection and Justification

We are proposing a machine-learning-based solution which is trained to manage traffic autonomously. Li [7] used an ensemble of machine learning methods for approximately the same purpose but in their study they used SVM, random forest and AdaBoost for pattern recognition and their primary goal was vehicle classification.

Hence the use of Machine learning methodology to detect anomalies and patterns is proven to be effective. Hence, the reason we also opted for Machine Learning Algorithm Random Forest for our use case. Random Forest was specifically used because it is an ensemble method combining a number of decision trees. Additionally, it is able to handle high-dimensional data which can capture complex relationships between features.

Lastly, traffic patterns are mostly non-linear hence random forest's ability to capture such patterns is also one of the reasons we chose this. Consequently, feature importance measure and robustness make this the perfect technique for our solution.

4.3 Scalability and Technological Feasibility

In a post by NxtLive [9], they discuss the characteristics of random forest and point out the fact that Random Forest can handle thousands of input variables without the need for variable

deletion. This means that it is perfect for large scale projects where huge amounts of data is stored and processed.

In addition to that, the Random Forest algorithm is fairly easy to parallelize as it runs multiple decision trees. This is also the reason it is a perfect fit for scalability and the ever increasing traffic network. This is an important point when it comes to the cost structure and the deployment on large scales. As we have to make use of the infrastructure already implemented with minimum additions.

We are aware that most cities for example Barcelona, Islamabad and Mumbai have cameras installed at every traffic signal. But through research and personal experience the installation of these cameras took a significant amount of investment from local governments but proved to be not as efficient as their main focus was to regulate traffic laws.

As per an article of CCTV ON RENT [4], Mumbai's road surveillance has a huge potential which is unexplored. As per my personal experience in Islamabad the capital of Pakistan and portrayed as a SAFE CITY [13] the traffic signals were mainly installed to regulate traffic violations but fail to do even that as all traffic violations are penalized by physical traffic wardens. Hence, data from these systems is openly available and we can use the already used infrastructure to retrofit in our solution and not worry about hardware compatibility.

Random forests were considered a black box but due to recent technological advancements specifically Shapley Additive explanations (SHAP) which can provide insights into the decision-making process of the model and advocating the fact for the Explainable AI potential.

4.4 Challenges in AI Adoption

There are always technical and non-technical challenges in such large scale projects, some of them are anticipated and projected to counter while the others, you don't see coming. There were several challenges faced by the team however the most complex ones are discussed and are as follow,

- **Data Quality Issues:** One of the first anticipated challenges was the inconsistency and low quality of data from legacy infrastructure. Much of the collected data was inconsistent, and lacked clarity due to which it was not suitable for training modern AI models. To address this, a significant data cleaning effort was required, and new devices had to be installed to gather higher-quality and more versatile data. This setup took almost a month, causing delays.

Versatility was essential, as biased data could lead to biased outcomes. New cameras were installed at selected intersections in alpha testing sites to overcome limitations in older equipment. As noted by Alam [2] from the University of the Cumberland, historical trend analysis often fails to adapt to real-time conditions and cannot predict anomalies due to its reliance on outdated data.

A related case study from the Los Angeles Smart City initiative showed that initial inefficiencies were caused by incompatible legacy systems, and integrating these systems required additional investment to improve accuracy.

- **Training Challenges:** According to Poonam [11], AI traffic management systems demand expertise in computer vision, machine learning, and predictive analysis—skills that many municipalities lack. This was also true in our case. Although anticipated, the rapid pace of project development left us underprepared in terms of skilled manpower.

An upskilling program became essential. As highlighted by Numalis [?], approximately 43% of organizations face AI talent shortages, often resulting in project delays. Many smart city projects have only succeeded after prioritizing personnel training.

- **Privacy and Security Concerns:** This emerged as the most significant challenge. Public distrust in AI, especially regarding real-time surveillance, raised strong concerns. Monitoring activities—whether for data collection or implementation—sparked debates on individual privacy.

For example, ReStack [12] reports that the deployment of AI-powered surveillance cameras in New York City’s subway system, intended to detect unpaid entries, ignited privacy debates despite its intended security purpose. These concerns must be addressed with transparency and strong data governance policies.

Hence, to counter this businesses must ensure that their data protection practices for the data in storage and in transit are up to the industry standards and being transparent to the general public in such matters is the best way to go about these situations.

So, in a nutshell following were the major challenges that were faced by the leadership but timely solution to these challenges made sure that the obstructions don’t gain a lot of resistance.

5 Implementation Plan

The implementation plan is divided into three parts, the teams, business metrics and operational decisions.

5.1 Organizational Structure

The organizational teams are divided into two parts: internal and external teams. The internal team is directly connected to the operation of the project and three main teams are involved, AI and Data Science Team which consists of our AI and ML engineers responsible for developing and fine tuning the models. Then comes our Data Analysts, who are responsible for the data used for training and decision making and lastly our Software Developers which are responsible for integration of the models with the infrastructure and the development operations that follow.

The second team involved internally is the IT and Infrastructure Team which consists of our Network Engineers responsible for cloud and edge computing framework. Our Cybersecurity specialists in charge of security and protection of intellectual property and sensitive data from cyber attacks and lastly our System admins responsible for administrative tasks in context of servers, databases and such.

The third and final team involved internally is our Traffic Operations and Engineering Team. This team consists of traffic engineers providing domain expertise, urban planners ensuring the implementation of AI is in accordance with the long-term infrastructure goals and operations manager responsible for supervising coordination in traffic control centers.

These are the teams which are not directly involved with the project but play a major role in overall success of the project. It consists of two major teams. The first one being Policy and Compliance Team which consists of our legal and ethical advisors addressing the ethical and moral use of AI and has Government Liaisons responsible for approvals of regulations and such.

Second comes our Public engagement and Training Team. This is also a very important aspect and consists of Public Awareness Officers responsible for education of citizens regarding the AI technology and gathering of feedback. Then we have Change Management Experts which ease the public into AI adoption and workforce transition and finally our Training Coordinators responsible for up-skilling of staff by developing AI training programs.

5.2 Business Metrics and KPIs

We are dividing our KPIs such that they are measurable and have key responsibilities to reach that KPI.

- **Intersection Delay Reduction**

Minimize wait times at traffic signals and improve overall traffic flow.

- Goal: Reduce average intersection wait times by 30% within the first 12 months.
- Achieve a 15% reduction in wait time during the first 2 quarters.
- Ensure 90% of traffic lights dynamically adjust based on congestion.
- Increase throughput by 20% with no bottlenecks.

- **Traffic Volume Management**

Optimize road usage by balancing traffic loads across intersections.

- Goal: Maintain average road occupancy below 85% during peak hours.
- Improve signal timing accuracy to handle 95% of traffic fluctuations.
- Reduce lane underutilization by 25% using signal prioritization.

- **Incident Response Efficiency**

Ensure faster clearance for emergency vehicles and better congestion management.

- Goal: Reduce emergency vehicle response time by 40%.
- Improve rerouting efficiency by 35% for congestion reduction.
- Ensure 80% of signals prioritize emergency vehicles within 5 seconds of detection.

- **Maintenance Cost Reduction**

Lower operational expenses associated with traffic infrastructure.

- Goal: Decrease maintenance costs by 25%.
- Reduce human intervention by 50%.
- Extend hardware lifespan by 30%.

- **Adoption Rate & Public Acceptance**

Ensure high public acceptance and usability of the system.

- Goal: Achieve 75% positive feedback within the first 12 months.
- Launch 3 public awareness campaigns.
- Reach a 50% adoption rate across metropolitan areas.

5.3 Operationalization

The roadmap of integrating AI into the operation is divided into integration roadmap and Change management Strategies. First we shall discuss the integration roadmap.

- **Feasibility Analysis and Approvals**

In the first stage, the goal is to conduct a feasibility analysis to determine whether the projected outcomes are viable. This involves technical, financial, and legal assessments. The primary objective is to secure approvals from local authorities and ensure compliance with local traffic regulations.

- **Development Stage**

Once prerequisites are fulfilled, the project enters a 9-month development phase. During this stage, AI models are trained and fine-tuned, and the necessary infrastructure for alpha testing is set up. All critical system components are developed and prepared for testing.

- **Pilot Deployment**

After development, pilot deployment is initiated using A/B testing. High-volume intersections are selected to deploy the system, monitor its real-time performance, and collect user and system feedback for iterative improvements.

- **AI Model Refinement**

Based on feedback from pilot testing, hyperparameters are adjusted and the models are further fine-tuned. Continuous improvement is supported through feedback loops and enhanced predictive modeling to improve accuracy and reliability.

- **Large-Scale Deployment**

Following successful testing and refinement, the system is deployed on a larger scale across city-wide networks. This involves expanding from pilot zones while utilizing existing infrastructure to minimize the need for new installations.

- **Post-Development Monitoring**

After full deployment, key performance indicators (KPIs) are tracked and analyzed. A real-time monitoring dashboard is implemented to enable continuous performance tracking and reporting. Transparency with the public is emphasized through open access to results and system operations.

The change management strategies are divided as follows,

- **Hybrid Supervision**

At the start it is a compulsory need for human intervention when it comes to supervision and monitoring hence we are using a hybrid model to monitor our systems to ensure they are working as planned. One thing to note is that human dependance is decreased here because during system failures the number one priority is to maintain the balance between human oversight and automation. This is done so that in future no human intervention is needed at any point.

- **Training of Staff**

We have to upskill the staff in every shape and form. For this we shall offer training programs which will be focused on AI operations, maintenance and troubleshooting, keeping in mind that state-of-the-art concepts are given in order for the staff to be skillful not only for the project but as a professional too.

5.4 Legal Framework

To accommodate AI tech into the general public changes need to be made hence we have to work with policymakers to do so. Collaboration with city planners and relevant authorities is important to ensure that our system complies with evolving traffic laws and standards.

Additionally, the whole project life-cycle must be aligned with the GDPR and EU AI act. This means that we must ensure that all personal data collected and processed must strictly adhere to the ethical frameworks such as data minimization, purpose limitation and user consent. Additionally, we must implement data protection measures both in storage and transit such as encryption, anonymization and secure storage. Moreover, complete transparency must

be showcased with users about how their data will be used and provide user-friendly access to data subject rights.

The algorithms must be explainable, fair and non-discriminatory as required by the EU AI Act. Lastly, we have to establish a clear governance framework to oversee data ethics both through internal auditing and external teams.

6 Technical Details

The following section includes the description of the data set and the procedure of model training and evaluation.

6.1 Data Description and Visualization

As mentioned earlier we are using random forests for our use case. Before doing anything we have to first analyze and visualize our data. Our data has 4 columns representing Timestamp, Junction, Vehicles and ID respectively. It captures the traffic flow at multiple junctions over time.

Figure 1: Traffic Flow Trends during the day through certain junctions

Figure 1, represents the traffic flow trends during the day. We can observe that vehicle counts vary and increase over time with peaks corresponding to rush hours. The peaks indicate times of high traffic volume which assist in identifying the critical periods for traffic management.

Figure 2, displays a boxplot representing the distribution of traffic volumes across different hours of the day. The central box represent the inquantile range which is where the majority of traffic data falls for each hour. The line represents the median traffic volume and the whiskers extend to show the range of typical traffic values. This visualization helps us identify the peak traffic hours and anomalies that may require special attention during the data preparation and model training.

Figure 3, depicts a line chart visualizing the average number of vehicles passing through different junctions over a given period of time. Each line corresponding to a different color represents a different junction. From the heart, it is evident that the junction 1, experiences consistently higher traffic flow, indicating potential congestion points.

Figure 2: Boxplot of Traffic Distribution Across Different Hours of the Day

Figure 3: Line Chart for average number of vehicles per junction

6.2 Model Training and Evaluation

As mentioned earlier, for this particular application we are using random forest, which makes an ensemble of decision trees, which will be perfect for our use-case scenario as it combines the output to improve accuracy and prevents overfitting. The first step involved data Preprocessing. Initially, we visualized the dataset (Figure 1,2 and 3) to identify underlying patterns, trends and anomalies. Significant anomalies were pruned and missing values were replaced by the mean of the respective feature column to maintain data consistency and reduce skew.

Using a heatmap we checked the correlation between features.

Figure 4: Feature Correlation Heatmap showcasing relationships between numerical features.

The underlying metric used to generate this heatmap is the Pearson correlation coefficient, which is calculated using the following formula:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2} \sqrt{\sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (1)$$

Here, r_{xy} measures the degree of linear correlation between two variables x and y , where \bar{x} and \bar{y} represent the mean values of x and y , respectively. The coefficient ranges from -1 (perfect negative correlation) to +1 (perfect positive correlation), with 0 indicating no linear correlation.

Following the correlation analysis we normalized the numerical features, which helps the model converge faster and reduce bias which may be caused by features with larger numeric ranges. Next, the dataset was split using a 80:20 ratio into training and testing, respectively. The split allows the model to learn from majority of data while preserving a portion for unbiased evaluation.

The Random Forest was then trained on the processed training data. It builds multiple decision trees on random subsets of data and features, aggregating their results to minimize variance. This allows the model to capture intricate patterns and non-linear relationships in the data across different junctions and times. At this stage, we configured the model with default hyperparameter, opting not to perform tuning yet. The tuning involves finding the optimal set of parameters θ that minimizes the loss function L on validation data, expressed as,

$$\theta^* = \arg \min_{\theta} L(\theta; X_{val}, y_{val})$$

where θ represents the hyperparameters such as number of trees, maximum depth, and minimum samples per leaf, and X_{val}, y_{val} are the validation features and labels.

Moving towards model evaluation, MSE was 16.79 indicating that the model's precision was reasonably close to actual values and was calculated using the formula,

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (2)$$

where n is the number of observations, y_i is the actual value, and \hat{y}_i is the predicted value for the i^{th} observation.

R squared was 0.85 advocating the fact that the model explains 85% of the variance in the traffic flow data.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (3)$$

where y_i is the actual value, \hat{y}_i is the predicted value, and \bar{y} is the mean of the actual values.

If we look into Feature Importance the column Junction and ID had 51.8% and 26.7% ,respectively. while the splitme-based features had less influence but still contributed to overall accuracy. A scatter plot of predicted V actual values showed a strong correlation, stating the fact that the model was accurate in making predictions.

Figure 5: Predicted vs Actual Values

The figure illustrates the relationship between the predicted and actual traffic flow values. The diagonal line represents the perfect prediction where predicted values equal actual values. The scatter of points represent how close the model’s prediction align with real observations.

7 Results and Discussion

Our model’s MSE is 16.79 which highlights that the models prediction are closer to actual traffic values. R squared value of 0.85 means that the model explains 85% of the variance in traffic flow data. The model can be dynamically adjust traffic signals based on real-time vehicle frequency and can help reduce unnecessary waiting times and prevent traffic jams at busy junctions.

In terms of environmental impact, smoother vehicle flow reduces stop-and-go driving, lowering emission and fuel consumptions, through this we will have less congestion and in-turn a smaller carbon footprint in urban areas. An important observation is the challenges

which may occur due to cultural differences because cultures affect how traffic signals are respected with some regions showing more signal jumping. Additionally, ensuring inclusive technology between urban and rural areas remains a concern.

However, this system will have a positive influence on a number of things. First and foremost traffic will be optimized resulting in less congestion, reduced travel time and more effective use of already existing infrastructure.

Secondly, it will have a positive environmental impact as cars will flow smoothly and won't have to slow down or speed up or come to a complete stop resulting in reduced carbon footprint. Lastly, it will improve public safety in countries such as Pakistan, India, Nepal and Bangladesh signal jumping is so common that it is considered a waste of time to stop at a signal. As per Times of India [10], in the last 5 years there has been a 33% increase in traffic signal jumps.

8 Ethical Considerations

As mentioned before we need to be mindful of the ethical concerns. Sensitive data needs to be handled with utmost care as real-time monitoring is often disturbing to hear and faces some resistance from the general public. Hence, transparency and industry standard data protection algorithms need to be used to keep the data secure. Additionally inclusivity needs to be kept in mind such high tech solutions are implemented in the urban areas but this leaves rural areas stranded and further widens the gap between the two, which will create a difference in how different areas and regions experience smart city technology.

9 Limitations

As per limitations of the project, we were and still are limited by the quality of the data. We need to further enhance the quality and quantity of the data attained to further improve the accuracy of the models. So, we must ensure that in future we invest in more robust data collection frameworks.

Lastly, real time monitoring and data processing requires strong computational power. Any lag or delay in processing can lead to delays in the dynamic changing of signals and delays can cause confusion which may undermine the entire purpose or result in a fatal accident. Hence, the limitation on computational power must be dealt with, without this infrastructure the potential of the automated traffic signals may not be fully realized.

10 Conclusion

In essence, this implementation of AI-powered traffic signals has been done theoretically and practically but still faces a lot of challenges to this day. The key findings from the project suggest that real-time data can significantly enhance the decision making ability of the power with of course appropriate computational power. Moreover, such metrics can be used by relevant businesses to optimize traffic infrastructure and improve urban mobility and with time invest in more robust data collection methodologies.

The requirement of robust data collection methods is also a recommendation. We need to make sure that unbiased and latest data is available to further enhance the capabilities of the model and with time train new models and move towards deep learning and reinforcement learning techniques.

11 Future Work

For the future one of the recommendations is to include a pedestrian counting system. As discussed pedestrian traffic is critical to the overall traffic flow hence optimizing that part of the traffic will give benefits too. This will not only balance the flow on both sides but also ensure that pedestrians are prioritized when needed without significant disruptions in the traffic flow itself.

In addition to that, we also can enhance the ability of the model to adapt to a versatile number of traffic scenarios such as special events, road closures or constructions. This will increase the robustness of the model and further increase the effectiveness when a number of different factors are at play closely mimicking the real life scenarios.

In conclusion, the project's application of AI driven Dynamic Traffic Signals has exhibited the unexplored potential in this sector. However, with further research and development the system can expand to sustainability considerations and further use of new AI technology to make way for safer, efficient and smarter cities.

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